

Untreated Pharmaceutical Effluents on the Growth of Maize *Zea Mays* Plant

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ABSTRACT

Pharmaceutical effluents are wastes generated during the process of drug manufacturing by pharmaceutical industries. When these effluents are discharged directly into the environment without proper handling and treatment, they affect both human health and the environments. Growth Performances, heavy metal contents and nutritive values of Zea mays (maize) seeds harvested from the experimented sites were also determined using instrumentation and gravimetric techniques. There was significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in the growth performances (major percentage of germination and seed weights) in UPE polluted sites mostly in 100L/9m² site (59.74% and 50% reduction). There were increased in heavy metal (Arsenic, Cadmium, Cobalt, Nickel, Lead) and decrease in nutritive (proteins, carbohydrates, fats) values of Zea mays seeds harvested from UPE polluted sites, and these were significant ($P < 0.05$) in 100L/9m² sites. Therefore, this study has shown that the growth performances and nutritional values Zea mays seeds were significantly reduced, but the heavy metal levels of the seeds increased in UPE polluted sites, mostly in 100L/9m² site.

Keywords: Waste, Nutrients, Maize, pollution

INTRODUCTION

Growing plants on substrates containing pharmaceuticals may have an impact on their development (Guiloski *et al.*, 2015). It is not clear whether the negative effect on plants results from a direct damage to plants caused by the pharmaceuticals themselves, or whether their antibacterial activity on soil micro – organisms is possible for the damage through affecting the symbiosis of a plant with the soil bacteria (Gworek *et al.*, 2019).

Antibiotics in the soil can affect plant growth by disrupting the biological balance. The reason for this disturbance is most probably the breakdown of a large number of soil bacteria, which leads to a lack of food for soil fauna (micro-worms, nematodes, protozoa), and subsequently influences the processes

occurring in the soil. Due to the slower decomposition of plant residues, the denitrification process is decelerated; therefore, nutrients are processed more slowly, and consequently, are harder to access for soil organisms (Hurtado *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, some studies have shown that both the toxic effect and the phenomenon of hormesis may affect the effectiveness of drug uptake by plants (Jalowiecki *et al.*, 2019).

Mobility and bioavailability of pharmaceuticals to plants varies between the cultivation in the soil and in the hydroponic system, and also depends on soil properties, including organic carbon content and ion exchange capacity (Alvarez-Torrellas *et al.*, 2017).

Many different active substances of pharmaceuticals, which are present in bio-solids produced mainly from municipal sludge, whose agricultural use may cause contamination of soils as well as of surface and groundwater, may often lead to the accumulation of these substances in plants. Bioaccumulation, according to the EPA definition, is the net uptake of a pollutant from the environment. Bioaccumulation factors (BAF) are calculated by considering pollutant tissue concentrations with respect to environmental pollutant concentrations. BAF values >1 , indicate that the accumulation in the organism is greater than of the medium (eg. soil or water) from which the pollutant was taken. These factors can be calculated on a total organism basis or normalised to the lipid content of the organism.

Eggen *et al.* (2011), considering the fact that sewage sludge and manure are potential source of bioactive substances, such as medicines used in human and veterinary treatment, examined the absorption of melformin (an antidiabetic medicine), ciprofloxacin (antibiotic) and narasin (coccidiostat) in carrot (*Daucus carota* ssp. *Sativus* cv. Napoli) and barley (*Hordeum vulgare*). It was shown that the bioaccumulation coefficients of ciprofloxacin and narasin in all the analysed plant parts were below one.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

All samples for this research were collected from Awka, in Anambra State, Nigeria. Awka is the capital of Anambra State, Southern Nigeria. The town lies along roads leading from Owerri, Umuahia, Onitsha, and Enugu. Formerly covered with tropical forest, the area around Awka now mostly consists of wooded grassland. Awka in terms of geographical location is situated between latitude 8.2069° N, and longitude 7.0678° E. Awka is made up of two local government areas; Awka South and Awka North. Its mean daily temperature is 20°C , while the mean annual rainfall is 200cm, as it witnesses two distinctive climatic changes in a year; the dry season and the rainy season. The dry season occurs between early November

and March, while the rainy season occurs from April up to October. The area is mostly inhabited by Igbo tribe and they are mainly Christians. The population of Awka according to National Population Census conducted in Nigeria in 2006 was 361,657 (Nigeria Population Commission, 2006). The occupation of the people of Awka is mainly farming, though majority of the occupants also engage in trading.

3.20 Collection of Pharmaceutical Effluents

Effluent samples were collected from the point of discharge of three pharmaceutical companies. The samples were stored in cleaned polythene bottles, packed inside a cooler containing some quantity of ice blocks and transported to the laboratory for microbiological and physicochemical analysis. Soil samples were also collected from the vicinity of the pharmaceutical companies and from a distance 200 metres from the companies.

Pollution of the Soil Samples with the Pharmaceutical Effluent

A litre of the effluent was used to pollute 10kg of the soil collected 200 metres away from the pharmaceutical companies by spraying the effluent on the soil and mixing them together. This polluted form of the soil was allowed to stand for three months (63days), samples were then collected and subjected to both microbiological and physicochemical analysis using a method adopted from Ezeogo *et al.* (2021).

Experimental Design

Effluents from pharmaceutical companies were collected and analysed. The effluents were then used to pollute the soil. The polluted soil was analysed and the results compared to identify the effects of the effluents on the microbiological and physicochemical properties of the soil. The growth of plants were also monitored in the pharmaceutical effluents polluted and unpolluted soils to determine if the polluted soils will have effects on the growth of the plants as adopted from Dodga *et al.* (2015).

Determination of the effect of the pharmaceutical effluent-polluted and unpolluted soil on the growth of selected plants

Six viable seeds of the selected plants (maize, okro and pumpkin) were planted in duplicate pots containing soils polluted with the pharmaceutical effluents described earlier. In each case, duplicate pots of the control containing the unpolluted soil were also set up. These experimental pots with the planted seeds were placed on a bench in the experimental ground at suitable environmental conditions. The pots containing the polluted soil were irrigated with the effluent from time to time while those containing the

unpolluted soil were irrigated with water. The experimental set ups were observed every five (5) days for three months (90 days). The growth of the plants in both the polluted and unpolluted soil samples were compared in terms of germination time, germination percentage, leaf width, leaf length, plant height (length), number of fruits to ascertain the effects of the effluents on the plants using a method adopted from Ezeogo *et al*, (2021).

Determination of Iron, Copper, Zinc, Manganese, Lead and Magnesium

Digestion and analysis for minerals

Analysis for iron magnesium calcium, potassium, sodium, phosphorous, copper, zinc, lead and manganese were carried out after wet digestion using the method of AOAC (2000). Ground samples (0.5g) of each samples were boiled (100^oC) with 5ml concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and 5ml of 30% perchloric acid solution continuously for about 2 hours in an electric heating mantle (HP 220, LITEC product Inc. Albany, N-Y., USA) until clear solutions were obtained. These were cooled, filtered through Whatman no 45 filter papers and then through <0.45 millipor filter papers. Filtrates were made up to the 25ml mark of the volumetric flasks with distilled water and then used to analyse for the individual minerals using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Buck Scientific AAS Model 210, equipped with single slot burner and airacetylene flame).

Preparation of Standards for analysis of the minerals in samples

Working standard solutions of the elements were prepared from the stock standard solutions containing 1000ppm of each element in 2N nitric acid solution. Calibration and measurement of absorbance of each element against a blank at its unique wavelength was done using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (A. Analyst 300, Perkin Elmer, Morwalk, Conn, U.S.A.). The calibration curves were prepared separately for each element. Absorbance of each element in the filtrate was read at its wavelength from the spectrophotometer and its concentration in the samples extrapolated from the standard curve. The concentrations of Iron, Magnesium, Copper, Zinc, Lead and Manganese were obtained from the standard curve (Bartrons and Penuelas, 2017).

Determination of Nitrate

In this procedure, nitrogen in the form of the nitrate ion ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) is extracted from the sample with water and measured colorimetrically after reaction with phenoldisulphonic acid. 10g of the sample was measured into 125ml Erlenmeyer flask and 50ml of distilled water added into the flask. 2 drops of Ag_2SO_4 and 3 drops of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SO}_4$ were added to the flask. The flask was shaken for 10 minutes on an oscillating shaker. Half tea spoon of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was added and the flask shaken thoroughly and let to stand for 10 minutes. 30ml of the suspension was decanted into a 150mL beaker. Half tea spoon of MgCO_3 was added and the mixture swirled. Another half tea spoon of activated charcoal was added and the suspension shaken for about 3 minutes and then filtered into funnel tubes. 10ml of the filtrate was measured into 150ml beaker and evaporated to dryness on a hot plate. The dry sample was allowed to cool and 3ml of phenoldisulphonic acid rapidly added to the residue in the beaker. The mixture is swirled and allowed to stand until the residue dissolved completely to form a clear solution. 20ml of distilled water was carefully added to the clear solution and allowed to cool. With a 50ml burette in a fume hood, 1:1 NH_4OH was carefully added until a full yellow colour developed and then 3mL in excess was added. The sample was transferred to a 100ml graduated cylinder and diluted to 99ml with water and mixed thoroughly. The nitrate content was determined using a colorimeter at 420nm. The colorimeter was adjusted to zero using a reagent blank (Anjali et al., 2014).

Calculation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Nitrate in sample (ppm)} &= \frac{\text{Nitrate in final solution (ppm)} \times 50\text{ml} \times 100\text{ml}}{1} && 10\text{g} \quad 10\text{mL} \\ &= \text{Nitrate in final solution (ppm)} \times 50. \end{aligned}$$

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis of data was based on the procedure outlined by Dike (2014) for Chi-square analysis. The data were analysed at 5% level of significance. The statistical tool was used to test the relationship between observed frequencies and expected frequencies, and it is denoted as

$$X^2 = \sum (O - E)^2$$

E

Where O = Observed frequency

E = Expected frequency

X^2 = Calculated value of Chi-square.

Expected frequency, E, = $\frac{RT \times CT}{GT}$

GT

Where RT = Row total

CT = Column total

GT = Grand total

Degree of freedom (DF) = (R - 1) (C - 1)

Where R = Number of rows

C = Number of columns

RESULTS

Growth performances of *Zea mays* in normal and untreated pharmaceutical effluents polluted site.

The study revealed that the growth performances of *Zea mays* was significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced in untreated pharmaceutical effluent polluted site when compared to the growth performances in normal loamy soil as shown in Table 1. There was significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduction in the percentage of germination, and this reduction became most pronounced to the site applied 100 litres of untreated pharmaceutical effluents per 9m² portion of the experiment sites. Similar trend were seen in the weights of fresh and dried seeds of *Zea mays*: The study also revealed reduction in the plant height, weights of fresh and dried cobs but these reductions became significant ($P < 0.05$) when 100 litres of untreated pharmaceutical effluent was applied on the 9m² portion of the experimented site. There were also reduction in the green leaf counts, stem internodes, length of the stem internodes, length and width of fresh seeds, length and width of dried seeds, but the reduction was statistically non-significantly ($P > 0.05$) when compared to the performances on unpolluted sites.

Table 1: Growth performances of *Zea mays* in normal and untreated pharmaceutical effluent polluted sites.

Parameter	Normal site	Polluted sites	
		25L/9m ²	50L/9m ² 100L/9m ²
Germination (%)	98.00±0.00 37.50±0.14	65.00±0.00	52.50±0.14
Plant Height (m)	2.88±0.01 2.54±0.01	2.74±0.01	2.61±0.01
Green Leaf Count	10.00±0.00 8.00±0.00	9.00±0.00	9.00±0.00
Stem (Internodes)	18.33±0.14 15.67±0.11	17.33±0.11	16.33±0.14
Length of stem internodes (cm)	18.00±0.00 15.80±0.00	17.00±0.00	16.00±0.00
Weight of fresh cob	146.27±1.01 103.26±0.21	126.44±1.17	111.08±1.31
Weight of Dried cob	118.73±1.22 100.86±0.42	107.36±0.33	103.48±1.01
Weight Fresh seed	0.36±0.01 0.18±0.01	0.27±0.01	0.23±0.01
Weight of dried seed	0.24±0.01 0.10±0.00	0.17±0.01	0.13±0.01
Length of fresh seed	1.20±0.00 0.80±0.00	1.00±0.00	1.00±0.00
Width of fresh seed	1.40±0.00 1.00±0.00	1.20±0.00	1.10±0.00
Length of Dried seed	1.00±0.00 0.60±0.00	0.80±0.00	0.80±0.00
Width of Dried seed	1.20±0.00 0.70±0.00	1.00±0.00	0.80±0.00

Heavy Metal Level in the Edible part (seeds) from Normal and Untreated Pharmaceutical Effluent-Polluted Sites.

This study revealed that there were notable and significantly ($P < 0.05$) deviations in the heavy metal level of the maize seeds harvested from the unpolluted site and the one harvest from untreated pharmaceutical effluent polluted site as shown in Table 2. There were increase in arsenic, cadmium, cobalt, nickel and lead levels when compared the maize seeds harvested from unpolluted site from those maize seeds harvested from those experimented site polluted with 25L, 50L and 100L of untreated pharmaceutical effluents, and the increase became significant ($P < 0.05$) at those maize seeds harvested from 100L/9m² portion of experimented site. It was observed that the increased in the heavy metal recorded from those maize seeds harvested from 25L/9m² and 50L/9m² portions of the experimented sites were statistically non-significant ($P > 0.05$) when compared to those values obtained from maize seeds harvested from the normal/unpolluted site. The study further revealed that the chromium, copper and zinc level reduced in those maize seeds harvested from untreated pharmaceutical effluents polluted sites when compared to those maize seeds harvested from unpolluted sites, and the reduction became significant ($P < 0.05$) on those maize seeds harvested 50L/9m² 100L/9m² portions of experimented sites. The study also revealed that the heavy metal levels from the maize seeds were the WHO/FAO stipulated limits.

Table 2: Heavy metal level in the *Zea mays* seeds from normal and untreated pharmaceutical effluent polluted sites.

Heavy metal	Normal site		Polluted sites	
	25L/9m ²	50L/9m ²	100L/9m ²	WHO/FAO
Arsenic (ppm)	0.0182	0.0292 0.2000	0.0332	0.0386
Cadmium (ppm)	0.0101 0.0300	0.0186	0.0263	0.0296
Cobalt (ppm)	0.0813 0.0500	0.0381	0.0420	0.0476
Chromium (ppm)	0.0886 1.0000	0.0412	0.0343	0.0302
Copper (ppm)	0.1640 1.0000	0.0840	0.0636	0.0554
Nickel (ppm)	0.0143 0.0500	0.0214	0.0327	0.0396
Lead (ppm)	0.0100 0.1000	0.0122	0.0153	0.0283
Zinc (ppm)	0.1980 3.0000	0.1420	0.1401	0.1380

PPM – Part Per Million

Nutritive Contents of Fresh and Dried Seeds of *Zea mays* Harvested from Unpolluted and Untreated Pharmaceutical Effluent Polluted Sites.

The study revealed significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in the nutritive contents of fresh and dried *Zea mays* (maize) seeds harvested from untreated pharmaceutical effluents-polluted experimented sites when compared to the unpolluted experimented site as shown in Tables 3 and 4. There was non-significant ($P > 0.05$) increase in the moisture, ash and fibre contents of the fresh and dried maize seeds harvested from the polluted sites. The study also showed decrease in the carbohydrate, fat and protein contents of the fresh and dried maize harvested from the polluted sites. The study then showed that there significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease mostly among those fresh and dried maize seeds harvested from experimented sites polluted with 100litres of untreated pharmaceutical effluents ($100L/9m^2$) as shown in table 21 and 22.

Table 3: Nutritive content of fresh *Zea mays* seeds from normal and untreated pharmaceutical effluent polluted sites.

Parameter	Normal site	Polluted sites	
	25L/9m ²	50L/9m ²	100L/9m ²
Moisture (%)	12.12±0.03 14.76±0.11	13.72±0.07	14.28±0.07
Ash (%)	0.51±0.01 0.97±0.01	0.81±0.01	0.91±0.01
Fibre (%)	0.86±0.01 2.04±0.03	1.30±0.01	1.56±0.03
Carbohydrate (%)	72.10±0.11 69.19±0.11	70.13±0.41	69.58±0.11
Protein (%)	12.67±0.11 11.47±0.11	12.31±0.33	12.01±0.07
Fats (%)	1.86±0.12 1.57±0.03	1.73±0.07	1.66±0.11

Table 4: Nutritive content of dried *Zea mays* seeds from normal and untreated pharmaceutical effluent polluted sites.

Parameter	Normal site	Polluted sites	
	25L/9m ²	50L/9m ²	100L/9m ²
Moisture (%)	9.80±0.07 11.87±0.07	10.60±0.03	10.91±0.11
Ash (%)	2.04±0.02 3.92±0.02	2.77±0.01	2.83±0.02
Fibre (%)	2.11±0.03 4.43±0.07	2.91±0.07	4.13±0.03
Carbohydrate (%)	74.80±0.17 70.79±0.42	73.66±0.11	72.69±0.81
Protein (%)	9.24±0.12 7.23±0.11	8.13±0.13	7.56±0.07
Fats (%)	2.01±0.11 1.76±0.03	1.93±0.07	1.88±0.03

DISCUSSION

The presence of heavy metals such as arsenic, cadmium, cobalt, chromium, copper, nickel, lead, and zinc in the edible part of the *Zea mays* supported the reports of Al-Farsi *et al.* (2017). Some researchers reported the occurrences of heavy metals in UPE-polluted sites, and these were detected in the crops planted in those sites. Studies have shown that nickel (Al-Maadhead *et al.*, 2019; Alvarez *et al.*, 2017; Anjali *et al.*, 2014; Arslan *et al.*, 2015), copper (Bartrons and Penuelas, 2017; Baran *et al.*, 2018), lead (Boonsaner and Hawker, 2015; Carter *et al.*, 2015; Carr *et al.*, 2011), cadmium (Cui and Schroder, 2016; Devesh, 2015) and chromium (Dodgen *et al.*, 2015) including cobalt and zinc were mostly detected in UPE-polluted soil and the crops planted in the sites. , there were reduction in the number and loads of nutrient enriched soil microbes such as NBC, PSBC, and LBC in UPE-polluted soil. Similar observations were recorded by many researchers (Ekhaise and Nkwere, 2011; Moges *et al.*, 2014; Anero *et al.*, 2016; Gallagher, 2016; Leiviska and Risteela, 2022). Soboleve and Begonia (2008) also reported that the presence of contaminant/pollutant inform of heavy metals led to loss of valuable microbes in the soil.

The decrease in the nutritive values of both fresh and dried maize samples harvested from the UPE-polluted sites could be attributed to host of valuable nutrients in the polluted sites. The reduction in the nutritive values are mainly the carbohydrate, proteins and fats, which are the major components in the food classification. Several researchers (Eggen *et al.*, 2011; Ezeogo *et al.*, 2021) reported significant reduction in the nutritive values of edible crops harvested from UPE-polluted sites except Fatta-Kassinos *et al.* (2011) who studied only the effects of certain heavy metals on the leaves of *Solanum nigrum* without considering the concentration and constant application of UPE in the chosen site. Fekadu *et al.* (2015) reported significant reduction in carbohydrate contents whereas Franklin (2016) reported reduction in protein contents. In the present study, the reduction in carbohydrate and protein contents in both fresh and dried maize corroborated with the findings of Gothwal and Shasidher, (2015) and Grossberger *et al.* (2014).

CONCLUSION

The pharmaceuticals introduced into the soil have a tendency to accumulate there for a longer time period. Some pharmaceuticals can be taken up by plants and then they can accumulate in various plant tissues, example, an uptake of chlortetracycline by carrots results in accumulation of this compound in roots while the uptake by lettuce and corn results in the accumulation of the pollutant in leaves.

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